

AUTOMATIC HUMAN FOLLOWING SHOPPING CART

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ABSTRACT

Nowadays, supermarkets are almost developed with much technological advancement. People purchase different items from the supermarkets and put them into a cart because it is the easiest way used in supermarkets to carry goods. However, throughout the whole process of shopping, customer must push the heavy weight of the cart manually by their own effort. To overcome this problem, we are introducing a new idea called “Human following cart for shopping malls” With the use of this cart, customers can enjoy their shopping and pay more attention on their shopping list without the need of pushing shopping cart. It will follow the customer throughout the shopping period leaving a certain distance. If the customer will stop then the cart will also stop at maintained distance by using Ultrasonic distance sensors. The cart will follow the customer by using IR sensors including transmitter and receiving modules.

CHAPTER NO1

INTRODUCTION

The shopping center is a place where people from all walks of life can get together their daily requirements such as food products, clothing and hygiene items, garden appliances and other electrical appliances. Due to public demand, the number of small and large shopping malls continues to increase over the years. Therefore, the level of improvement of shopping mall and infrastructure changes. There are many areas that need improvement to provide consumers with a high quality shopping practice. Consumers often face problems while shopping.

Nowadays, in mall for purchasing variety of items it requires cart. The client must pull the cart from the shelf to the shelf (sack to stack) to collect items. A lot of energy is needed when shopping. However, cart were needed in the supermarkets. A lot of goods in the shopping cart would be to push or pull, so the customers will limit the activity of the hand. When the customer focuses on pushing the cart, buyers often miss plenty of products that are sold in the supermarket and will only buy important products and of course this could damage the supermarket.

Technology provides retailers with an opportunity to reduce the costs, improve services, and provide customers with rapid participation and personalized response services. Robots around the world, entering malls, shows that Android technology is gaining ground.

In order to provide the best service, a cart was needed that could automatically follow the human movement. Direction can be detected using power transducers, sensors or an detector.

In current time, Automatic customer following cart is necessary for everything to run a life. Automatic customer following cart has become a necessary part of our life. In current time, Automatic customer following cart is necessary for everything to run a life. Automatic customer following cart has become a necessary part of our life. Due to the increase in population, all things in this world are increasing such as shopping malls, Mega mart, and Air ports etc. That is why we required a Automatic customer following cart instead of manually customer following cart.

1.1 Motivation

The motivation behind this project is to provide better the shopping any where i.e mega malls grocery stores etc. This project is to make more easier the shopping, avoiding dragging or pushing the cart and to increase the concentration of customers on items rather than pushing cart.

1.2 General Description of the Project

The Automatic Human Following Shopping Cart is consist of three main parts, Mechanical Hardware, Electrical Hardware, the Software part interfacing to the system through IR receiver and transmitter module, the programming part is to prepare logics and proper programming of the Cart. As we are going to design a cart which move heavy loads, therefore we used Power Window Motors which are very high torque motors, these motors are connected to 4 channels relay and the four channels relay is directly connected to 12 volts battery to provide power for the motors. And the relay is operated by arduino transmitting logics to four channels relay through analog output pins connected to four input pins of the 4 channels relay. The arduino will be directed by means of sensors.

1.2.1 Hardware part

Hardware of the project comprises of:

1.2.1.1 Electrical Hardware

The Electrical Hardware Includes the designing of circuit, proper connections with four channels relay, DC motors, IR transmitter and receiver modules, Ultrasonic distance sensors and the Variable module for 12 volt DC to 5 volts DC for the circuit power supply.

1.2.1.2 Mechanical Hardware

The Mechanical Hardware includes designing and and balancing of the Shopping Cart. And fixing DC motors and tyres in the back portion of the cart. So we purchase a shopping cart and weld DC motors wih back legs of the Cart with the help of a metal sheet and also weld tyres with the shafts of the DC motors

1.2.2 Software part

The software part of this project includes proteus for simulation and programming of the Arduino Uno to interface with the help of sensors.

1.3 Problem Statement

Nowadays, moving a shopping cart is difficult task in shopping malls because of weight of shopping stuff. The manual cart in mega malls, Superstores, airports is pushed by the customers is tough. These types of carts are not User friendly specially for Older People. This problem can be solved by introducing an automatic cart also known as "Automatic Human Following Cart" by using different sensors. With the use of this cart customer can enjoy their shopping and pay more attention on their shopping list without the difficulty of pushing or pulling shopping cart.

1.4 Problem Solution

The project is to make the shopping much easier for the customers, the customers can select and put things in the shopping cart with more attention without pushing or pulling the shopping cart that is a difficult task during shopping.

1.5 Aims and Objectives

1.5.1 Aims

- Developed automation techniques in a simple or manual Shopping Cart.
- The Automatic Following Shopping Cart will be customer friendly throughout the whole shopping.
- To make the customers free handed and more attentive towards the items in shopping centres.

1.5.2 Objectives

- To implement the Automation System in a manual shopping cart.
- To be able to understand the Automation System implemented in the manual cart.
- To understand the principle of the sensors and their applications.
- To be able to select appropriate or suitable sensors for certain application.
- To be able to design and build the whole circuit and proper connections.
- To design such an automated Cart that is Automatically Human Following.

1.6 Design Components

Following components are used

- Four Channel Relay(4 CH Relay)
- Manual Shopping Cart
- Arduino Uno
- Arduino Nano
- DC Power Window Motors
- 12 Volts Dry Battery
- 12 Volt DC Charger
- Ultrasonic Sensors
- Transmitter Module (IR)
- Receiver Module (IR)
- Relays
- 12 Volt DC to 5 Volt DC Module
- Glass Sheet
- Metal Sheets

1.7 Scope of the Project

As the population of the world increasing day by day. You will see rush at Airports, Superstores, Mega Malls, Industries and all other places where the manual cart is used. The people are much tired of using the manual cart. The Automatic Human Following Cart is suitable for such places that would require high man power for pushing or pulling the cart. The automated systems tend to be more expensive than manual system of cart, and operators of these cart will usually need to undergo significant training before the cart can be used effectively. The use of manual cart tend to be less expensive and far easier to use; they are also more easily serviceable, whereas automated system of cart may require lengthy troubleshooting and diagnostics.

1.7.1 Airports

The airports have also these manual carts that are used by passengers to move there bags from the conveyor belt to the car side. So this automatic human following cart will be more useful in airports to help the passengers avoiding them from pushing or pulling the cart. The condition is to make ensure that the cart can move in whole airport where the passengers are allowed to go in.

1.7.2 Mega Marts

The smart and passionate use of this automatic human following cart is one in mega marts that is more attended by people in daily life. The attractive thing is that people can freely shop items and put these things into the cart relax.

1.7.3 Industrial Usage

For the use of industries, our target point of this project is to help industry that need carry heavy tools from one point to another point. Thus this cart can reduce power by labour required to push the cart. When their need to carry a heavy tools in industries, it can be handled just by one labour because this cart can follow the labour. So It reduce the cost of workers hired.

1.8 Organization of Report

Chapter 1 Provides a brief introduction to the project work giving some information about the project. Problem statement and Solution also been discussed.

Chapter 2 Gives a brief introduction and overview about action of this project. Basic structure and mechanism to work is also discussed in this chapter. Basically it is the literature review of the project.

Chapter 3 Introduces different components used in this project and also highlights their features and working procedure.

Chapter 4 Discusses the methodology of our project in detail, how it was designed?

How it was constructed? Implementation of the project in which system discussed about how the component being implemented.

Chapter 5 Gives results and conclusion also included future suggestions for research in this area. Also how we enhance this project to get better results and how one can make it more efficient.

CHAPTER NO 2

LITERATURE REVIEW

An automatic line following cart, the road following cart is able to follow a human via line following strategies and it will follow black line. Considering the functional records that they developed, the research organization we discussed have made an automatic cart which follows the human with help of an Arduino mega to move forward the research group came up with the methodology and that they used sensors for developing this cart. Sensors to sense the route which the clients walk. Moreover, it is working on android device fixed in front. [1].

Automatic purchasing cart to lessen the time ingesting in supermarkets and malls. Whenever the customer puts a product to the cart RFID reader scanned it and product fee and fee displayed on LCD. ZIGBEE transmitter and receiver used to make a connection among cart and predominant computer server. Considering the research achieved via Mr. Yathisha and the institution they have focused particularly on billing aspect. The advanced cart can automatically comply with the consumer too [2].

Electronic shopping cart based on Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) technology. This cart contains a function to track the goods eg. Viewing the product name, expiry date and the cost, to display the items they have used a Liquid Crystal Display (LCD) screen. The drawback of the system is the cart does only the functions that are mentioned above. Thus the cart is electronic it does not cover the automatic travelling facility [3].

System designed to track the purchased objects the usage of a Quick Response (QR) code which evolved a cart to manage the products and do the automated billing with the help of an digital display. Through this system it does the billing process but the research is not finished with a totally automated cart. However, the battery of the cart need to be charged manually. Considering these information designed a cart which saves man strength is essential [4].

Multitasking shopping cart with use of RFID technology. This is embedded with the aspect automatic product identification and billing. To track the products, it uses the technology RFID which contains readers and tags placed on the products. Though this identify the

product through RFID the proposed system uses bar code reader to track the goods. Considering all the facts this cart does not perform multitasks as it describes. The developed research is based on more functionalities that is more time consuming and easy to handle [5].

A system named Intelligent Shopping Cart developed using RFID technology in additionally this module consist of a technology Zigbee go get product details from the main server. This project improves the time consumption such as it reduces the time which waste on long queues to pay the bills. Although the system consumes the time, developed cart which travels automatically saves more time and human power [6].

The IOT Based Cart is made in India which cheking the items purchased by using RFID tags techniques. When a customer puts an item which he want to purchase into the cart the RFID tags will detect the item and will able to show the price of the item. The carts with RFID tags are placed in all the marts. All the items in the shopping malls are equipped with RFID tags. Therefore, there is no way to travel the cart automatically but to put goods into the cart [7].

Shopping and automatic billing using RFID technology was developed by Vidyavardhaka College of Engineering in India. They have come up with an architecture with Radio frequency identification (RFID) and wireless technology to provide on spot billing in super markets. It uses the RFID based system application in the shopping cart and the RFID tags which is used security of the products. A Liquidcrystal display (LCD) that is fixed to the cart displays the product name, cost and the total of all purchased products. The bill is transmitted to the server end through the ZigBee technology. There's no Automatic travelling system to the cart. The research group has focused only in purchase tracking and billing only [8].

This research was developed for disabled customers. The research group implemented a cart which follows the customer. To chase the customer accurately and measure the position a laser beam and laser range sensor is used. A gyro sensor and a rotary encoder also used for fared chasing and have developed a mapping algorithm and an estimation method for searching the position of the customer. This cart is capable of following the customer only [9].

Automated shopping cart which can control using a remote. The structure of this cart consist of robotic structure and a keypad which is used to navigate the cart along the particular way. The Keypad has the inbuilt product code reader to read the bar codes and track the goods

purchased. The wireless billing system is made up of the ZigBee communication module [10].

Smart shopping cart for automated billing purpose, this cart is uses sensors and are connected wirelessly to the system and uses comparison algorithm of any image to calculate the bill without need of a customer. Customer does not need to waste their time staying in long queues to pay the bill at the managers. The cart is unable to start following the a customer automatically. The developed research is mainly based onthe automatically finding path and cart will move. Integrated with some functionalities such as an android tablet is used which is fixed in the cart to detect and track purchased goods and generate automatic bill. Furthermore, the cart is embedded with parking and charging automatically while the cart is parked in the slot [11].

Shopping cart with smart shopping system to reduce the time wastage of customer and to make the shopping life easier for the customer. This automatic cart is using Ultrasonic sensors to identify obstacle avoidance and android application to control. Moreover, this system helps users to find the products location which users RFID tags and readers for the identification phase [12].

Varsha Jalkote et al., developed a futuristic billing cart with using RFID and ZIGBEE technologies. Whenever customer put a product into the cart RFID scanner scanned it and product cost and the price bill displayed on the Liquid Crystal Display (LCD). By using ZIGBEE transmitter it takes product details which is stored in the main computer server of the supermarket. Thus the system is intelligent with the billing criteria it does not cover the aspects of the developed research “Follow Me” [13].

An cart was developed for patients navigation system for hospitals that uses an active RFID technology, IR sensors and Arduino. The purpose of the research is to operating and self supporting the patient cart Without wasting the power of human. Navigation part is done by RFID tags and readers. Considering the above mentioned facts research group developed an automated cart the main criteria that differs from the patient cart is that the system only navigates within the given path. The developed cart follows the man where he/she walks [14].

Intelligent cart for automatic billing in malls using RFID technology and internet server. Then the billing part is done in the cart itself. Product cost and name is showing on LCD. Thus the system is more intelligent with the use of bill system of the items, it does not cover that to fallow a human research “Follow Me” [15].

CHAPTER 3

THEORETICAL ASPECTS

3.1 Introduction

The rapid growing and advancement of modern technology has yield to the developments and inventions of modern equipments. These inventions have eased human significantly in all aspects of their daily lives. Robotics automation plays an increasingly important part in the global economy and also in daily experience. At present, for companies, the purpose of automation has shifted from growing productivity and reducing costs to broader issues

Our work on the project is the idea of automation in a manual shopping cart. This is the idea than can be implemented in different places where heavy loads are carrying from one point to another. That will be in shape of human friendly cart which will fallow the customer with so specified distance from the customer.

This report concentrates and focuses on the idea of implementation of the cart that will fallow customers. With one of all the available methods in the ongoing researches, definitely, the automation system should be improved.

The introduction of sensors based automation in an manual cart increase the speed and accuracy of the shopping in mega marts. The platform is majorly consists of Ultrasonic sensors, Four Channels Relay, Arduino Nano and Arduino Uno,, The arduino uno is programmed with PC or laptop to make the proper mechanism of cart that how the term "following" will be made more efficiently, The arduino uno will be the controller that will receive data from different sensors on these bases the arduino uno will give commands to the motor driver circuit (four channels relay) when to go forward, Backward, And when to be left or Right

This project consists of following main functions:

- Forward Movement
- Backward Movement
- Change of directions (Left, Right)
- Hardware implementation

3.2 Forward Movement:

This is the movement of the cart which will be done by power windows motors when both motors will rotate in forward direction. Now how these motor will rotate in forward direction The motors will operate on sensors base, When the IR transmitter module transmit data from the belt wore by the customer the IR receiver module to come forward and follow me then the IR receiver module will receive the data and transmit to the arduino uno the arduino uno will send commands to the motor driver relay circuit by mean of input pin (int1,int2,int3,int4) to make motors moving in forward direction until the cart reach a specified distance from the customer. This is the range that will be directed and controlled by Ultrasonic sensor installed in front of the cart. The ultrasonic sensor will not let the cart to touch or collide with the customer.

3.3 Backward Movement:

The Ultrasonic sensor is all set to measure distance of the customer and decide on the basis of distance measured, If the customer's distance detected by ultrasonic sensor is less from the specified distance of ultrasonic sensors the the motors will move in backward direction until the cart reach the specified distance and this will be done again and again if the customer's move towards the cart. The backward movement will be done when both the motors are rotating in backward direction.

3.4 left, Right Turn:

The changing of direction is a key and much necessary point in the cart, We have installed three IR receiver modules in the cart. The left turn will be directed by left IR receiver module sensor and Right turn will by right IR receiver module sensor. Thus when the the IR receiver module detect the customer from left or right sensor the command will be send to motor driver circuit through arduino uno to turn left or right.

3.5 Hardware Implementation

The Hardware structure of this project consists of a manual shopping cart which moves freely we have modified it to our desired mechanical structure. We cut the two freely movable tyres from back portion of the cart and then we use a metal sheet which we welded to the back legs of the cart. After this we make holes in the metal sheet according to the motor's screws then

the shaft are welded to the motors and fixed in the metal sheet by screws. The project main hardware includes manual cart, Two metal sheets, One freely movable tyre, Two fixed tyres, Nuts, Screws, Shafts. 12 volts DC power window motors.

The Cart will be able to follow a Human with the help of an infrared sensor that will transmit a code 2704 continuously when the transmitter circuit is being started. When the 2704 code is received by front sensor the Cart will go forward, and when the code received by left or right sensor the car will turn accordingly

3.6 Mechanical Components

3.6.1 Manual Shopping Cart

The manual shopping cart is a tools carrier which moves freely in which direction the customer want to move. The manual shopping cart consist of two fixed movable tyres in back legs and two or one freely movable tyre the direction is changing with the help of these tyres installed in front of the cart. We take That manual cart and modified into our much needed structure. We implement the project in the manual cart. Simple we cut the back legs from the cart and design metal sheet that are welded. The manual cart we used in our project is the man frame of hardware and first step of the implementation of hardware of the project.

Size:: 730*450*880 mm

Figure 3.1: Manual Cart

3.6.2 Metal Sheets

The two metal sheets are designed for the DC power window motors that the motors are fixed in the metal sheets and each sheet is attached welded to the each legs of the cart in back portion these metal sheets provide strong support to the motors. There four holes in the metal sheet three for screws to tied motor and one holes is for the shaft of the motor as shown in the figure 3.4. The length of each metal sheet is 6 inches while width is 4 inches.

Figure 3.2: Metal Sheet

3.6.3 Shaft

There are two shafts welded at the ends of shafts of each motor. Each shaft is connected to a tyre. The motor rotates the shaft and hence the tyre starts moving. The length of each shaft is 2 inch.

Figure 3.3: Shaft

3.6.4 Nuts

The tyres are put into the shafts then for fixing and blocking the tyres nuts are used to prevent the tyres from missing and to make the tyres hardly to move with shaft thus when the shaft is moving then the whole tyre is rotating and the movement of cart occurs.

Figure 3.4: Nuts

3.6.5 Tyres

The tyres used in our project are made of hard plastic having a bearing in the center which we have blocked inside to not move freely but only move with shaft. The tyres has the capability to move 1 to 20 kg weight and are tough hard to break mean having strong stiffness.

Figure 3.5: Tyres

3.7 Electrical Components

Here some brief idea about the electrical equipment's/components used to construct the electrical part of the project such as

- 12 Volts DC Power Window Motors
- Four Channels Relay
- Arduino Uno
- Arduino Nano
- Buck converter (adjustable)
- 12 Volts Battery
- 12 Volt Battery Charger
- Ultrasonic Sensors
- IR Receiver Module
- IR LED transmitter
- M/F Cables
- Wires
- 5 volt cell

3.7.1 12 Volts DC Power Window Motors

A power window motor is a high torque DC motor that is used for sliding the glasses of auto doors. We used these motors because we are going to design an automated cart that will lift upto 15 kg weight. The power window motor is 12 volt DC motor. The no-load speed or speed when no torque is applied to the shaft of the power window motor is 95 rotations per minute (rpm) and because of no load the current consumes is less than 1.5 amperes. The current consumption is directly proportional to the load applied to the shaft of motor.

Figure 3.6: Power Window Motor

Specifications of Motors

The specifications of DC motor are:

- Motor Type: DC Power Window Motor
- Operating Mode: DC
- Voltage: 24 volts Max
- Current without Load: 1.5 Ampere max
- Current with Load: 15 Ampere max
- Mechanical lock
- 90 RPM

3.7.2 Four Channels Relay

Four channels relay is also called motor driver circuit that drive motor according to command given by the arduino. The four channels relay consist of 4 relays each relay has a combination of NO normally open and NC normally closed switches that are used for the motors. It has

four input pins, And a VCC and one pin GND. The four channels relay is operated by 5 volt DC source. The relay works on the basis of logics that are send by arduino. The logics are in the form of 1 or 0 that make the motor drive. The relay have input and output terminals and are designed to control the voltage supply.

Figure 3.7: Four Channel Relay

Pins description :

Pin Name	Description
Vcc	Power Pin(5v DC)
GND	Gnd
int1	Signal pin and control relay 1
int2	Signal pin and control relay 2
int3	Signal pin and control relay 3
int4	Signal pin and control relay 4
Com	Common pin of GND
NO	Normally open connection
NC	Normally closed connection
Middle Pin	Common connection for power

Figure 3.8: Pins Description[21]

Parameters:

[Name]: 4 Channels Relay

[Model]: SRD-05VDC-SL-C

[Size]: Size: 75mm (Length) * 55mm (Width) * 19.3mm (Height).

[Weight]: 61g.

[PCB Colour]: greenish

[Operating Mode]: DC

[Operating voltage]: 5 VDC

[AC Control]: 250 Volt, 10 Ampere

[DC Control]: 30 Volt, 10 Ampere. [20]

3.7.3 Arduino Uno

An arduino uno is computer programmable device with digital, Analog and power pins. The arduino uno has a usb port that can be used to program the arduino through computer the usb port can also be used as 5 vlot DC source for arduino. The arduino uno has a reset button which used for refreshing and emptying the arduino from programme. The arduino uno is a microcontroller board based on the ATmega328P which is the datasheet of its necessary components. It has 14 digital input/output pins in which 6 pins can be used as PWM outputs, 6 analog inputs, a 16 MHz quartz crystal, a USB connection, a power jack, an ICSP header and a reset button. The arduino uno contains everything needed that to support the microcontroller used in arduino uno, The UNO is the best board for getting started with those electronics that are controlling with help of coding. If any one is first to Uno experience tinkering with the platform, the board of UNO is the most robust board he can start playing with. The UNO is the mostly used and best board of the whole Arduino family.

Simply connect the arduino uno to a computer with a USB cable or connect it through an AC-DC 5 Volt power adapter or through 5 Volt battery to get started.

Figure 3.9: Arduino Uno[22]

3.7.4 Three Arduino Nano

The Arduino Nano is a small computer programmable bread board based on the ATmega328P (Arduino Nano 3.x). It has some related functionality as that of the Arduino Uno but one of its difference is package of jack. It has not only a DC power jack, and works with a Mini-B USB cable instead of a standard one as that are used in Arduino Uno. The Arduino Nano is used in this project, which is connected with IR transmitter LEDs and a 5 volt DC battery. This circuit is installed in the belt that will be worn by customers as the IR sensors be in back side of the customer. The IR transmitters send message to Arduino via infrared rays. The Arduino Nano can simply be operated by giving DC 5 volt Vcc.

Figure 3.10: Arduino Nano[23]

Specifications Of Arduino Nano

specifications of Arduino Nano are:

- Microcontroller ATmega328
- Operating Voltage : DC 5 V
- Input Voltage (limits): 6-20 V
- Digital Pins : 14 (of which 6 provide PWM Output)
- Analog Pins: 8
- DC Current per Pin: 40 mA
- Flash Memory: 32 KB
- Clock Speed: 16 MHz
- Measurements: 0.73" x 1.70"

3.7.5 Buck Converter (adjustable)

The Buck Converter is a device that is use for converting a dc Voltage from one level to another level. It is used in low power consumption electronic to step down 24/12 volts to the desired dc voltage. The buck converter a simple circuit and can be designed by a diploma holder also with a little bit experience of Electrical workshop.

Figure 3.11: Buck Converter[24]

The main advantage of the adjustable Buck Converter is to provide different voltages that needs to the projects or robots without making special dc supply for all components.

Technical Specifications

The specifications are:

- Input Voltage: 3.2V 40VDC
- Output Voltage: 1.25V 35VDC
- Max. Output Current: 3A
- Low Power Standby Mode: 80 μ A
- Operating Temperature: -45°C to +85°C

3.5.6 12 Volts Dry Battery

A battery is a stored source of charge, that can be used in various projects or robots. For the efficient and better performance of an electronic project you need to have a power bank in shape of a battery. The dry battery is made of Lead Acid that is more active material and having outstanding density to ensure the quality of battery. Using brass coated lead alloy battery terminals minimizes the impedance of connecting cells inside. With very little gas evolution, the water loss is minimized and service life is extended. Excess pressure and gas will be released which ensures safety. The case of the battery is made of ABS resin and cells are kept under internal pressure protects from outer shock or impact. The dry battery has more efficient duty cycle than ordinary batteries. In the figure a 12 volt 12 AH battery is given.

Figure 3.12: Battery [25]

Specifications Of Battery

Voltage	Amp/H	Length	Width	Height	Weight
12 Volts	12 AH	5.95"	3.86"	3.74"	8.38 lb

We used one Dry Battery in our project that is 12 volts and 12 ampere. The battery is directly connected to buck converter and the four channels relay. The connection with buck converter is to make a 5 volt source for the remaining circuit, while the four channels relay is to give 12 volt supply to motors through logic switches or relays.

3.7.7 12 Volts Battery Charger

The DC charger is a device used to charge a battery the charging capacity depends on the rate of current of a charger. In the figure a 12 volt 12 ampere Smart Fast charger is shown we have used also in our project. The Smart Fast charger has three modes of charging (1)Constant Current Mode: When the voltage of battery is lower than the value set by charger then the charger will work under constant current mode. (2) Constant Voltage Mode: To control the output voltage Pulse Width Modulation is used to ensure that the battery is full and avoid over charging. (3) Floating Mode: use to cut of the overcharging.

Figure 3.13: 12 Volt Battery Charger [26]

Features

- Max charging current:10A
- Rated input voltage:110-240V
- Adopt PWM charging mode, auto stop charging when the battery gets fully charged
- LCD screen display: Charging voltage/Battery capacity/Charging current
- Auto battery detection
- Applicable for gel battery and lead-acid battery

3.7.8 Ultrasonic Sensors

As indicated by the name the ultrasonic sensor is a device which used for measuring distance to an object by means of sound waves. Now how the sensor works, It measures the distance by sending a sound wave with a specific frequency and then waiting for that frequency to bounce back and noted the distance on this base. Since it is known that sound travels through air at about 344 m/s (1129 ft/s), you can take the time for the sound wave to return and multiply it by 344 meters (or 1129 feet) to find the total round-trip distance of the sound

wave. Round-trip means that the sound wave travelled 2 times the distance to the object before it was detected by the sensor; it includes the 'trip' from the sonar sensor to the object AND the 'trip' from the object to the Ultrasonic sensor (after the sound wave bounced off the object). To find the distance to the object, simply divide the round-trip distance in half.

Figure 3.14: Ultrasonic Sensors [27]

The accuracy of Ultrasonic sensor can be affected by the temperature and humidity of the air it is being used in. However, for these tutorials and almost any project you will be using these sensors in, this change in accuracy will be negligible. It is important to understand that some objects might not be detected by ultrasonic sensors. This is because some objects are shaped or positioned in such a way that the sound wave bounces off the object, but are deflected away from the Ultrasonic sensor. It is also possible for the object to be too small to reflect enough of the sound wave back to the sensor to be detected. Other objects can absorb the sound wave all together (cloth, carpeting, etc), which means that there is no way for the sensor to detect them accurately. These are important factors to consider when designing and programming a robot using an ultrasonic sensor.[27]

3.7.9 IR Receiver Module

The IR receiver module is a electronic component which receives IR (Infrared Radiations) from a IR transmitter. It is consist of a photo diode that is used as receiver head. The module receive infrared ray independently and output signals compatible with TTL level. The module has three pins VCC,GND and a Signal pin. It has DC 5 volts recommended operational voltage.

Figure 3.15: IR Receiver Module [28]

The infrared is a common, inexpensive, and easy to use for wireless communication e.g wirelessly the channels of a TV can be change through a remote and much more uses of IR sensors are available. We used three IR receiver module in our project one is in the front of the cart and other two modules are in the left and right sides of the cart. The middle pin is VCC and the negative signed pin is ground. So the remaining one is Signal or data pin

Specifications Of IR Module

- Acceptance angle: 90 °
- Operating voltage: 7-5.5V.
- Frequency: 37.9KHZ,
- Receiving distance: 18Meter.

3.7.10 IR LED Transmitter

An IR transmitter is a two lead light emitting diode (LED) that transmits infrared radiation and these radiations are detected and received by IR receiver module which has a photo diode which acts as a receiving head. A flash of invisible light from the LED transmitter is turned into instructions and thus received by the receiver module converting into electronically signals. This transmitter circuit consist of a power Bank that used for DC supply. An Arduino is also used to transmit a decimal code through IR transmitter circuit.

Figure 3.16: IR Transmitter Module [29]

3.7.11 M/F Cables

The male to female cables are connecting wires having a jack at one end and a pin that to inserted in the jack. The M/F cables used in projects related often with arduino. Because the arduino circuit has jacks which need male input pins. A male connector is commonly referred to as a plug and has a solid pin for a centre conductor. A female connector is commonly referred to as a jack and has a centre conductor with a hole in it to accept the male pin. In the given figure 3.17 40 pins of 20 cm pack is shown.[30]

Figure 3.17: M/F Cables

We use male to female connectors in our project. To make a neat and clean project you have to use the connector wires in your project.

3.7.12 Wires

A wire is a single, usually cylindrical, flexible strand or rod of metal. Wires are used to bear mechanical loads or electricity and telecommunications signals. Wire is commonly formed by drawing the metal through a hole in a die or draw plate. ... Wire comes in solid core, stranded, or braided forms.[31]

Figure 3.18: Wires

3.7.13 5 Volt Cell

A cell is a small storage device of charge. It may be rechargeable or not depends on it's type. We can say it is a rechargeable battery of smaller-sized and can be used for the operation of Arduino, Raspberry Pi, or Propeller, or anything else that works with low voltage. We used a small rechargeable cell in the belt circuit because that circuit consist of simple arduino nano and IR LEDs. So the cell is enough for these things. In the given figure a 3.7 Volts single battery is shown.

Figure 3.19: 5 Volt Cell [34]

CHAPTER NO 4

METHODOLOGY OF THE PROJECT

4.1 Introduction

After the description of components , the implementation phase is started. In this phase, the system is built to meet designed specification. This phase is concerned with the selection of technology, tools and the components used to develop the system. These decisions for this product are explained in this chapter. The theoretical works on a FYP project is turned into reality, when all the components of the project are bring together and implement the circuit diagram really by components. The four channels relay, arduino uno and dc motors we used in our projects are the key components of the project. Our project is controlling by different sensors, these sensors are IR receiver and transmitter also. And for obstacle detection Ultrasonic sensors are used. A successful project need a Flow charts and circuit diagrams explaining the function, design and development of the project. The designing of project need a platform data sheet of whole circuit and the flow chat that you can use step by step that is development of a project. Without a flow chart and proper initial block diagram a project may not be developed better. the each functional block and Complete flow chart of the project is shown in figure 4.1 below:

Figure 4.1: Block Diagram

First of all, We divided the project into two part, the circuit which is implemented on glass sheet is the receiver part that is the central controlling part of our project, and the second part is the transmitter part consisting of IR LEDs and arduino nano which are fitted in a belt. Thus when the customer wear the belt and turn on the cart circuit and the belt circuit by buttons then the cart will start following the customer if there is no obstacle in between. The cart will follow the customer until he stops. The cart will stop near the customer at a distance of 0.2 meter not colliding with him. This range is fixed in the programming and the range is detected by ultrasonic sensors colliding with him

4.2 Description and Design of the Project

The main functioning blocks involved in the project are presented and all technical details of each functioning block and its components are described in detail below.

4.2.1 Designing Manual Cart

We implemented our project in a simple or manual shopping cart. The cart is consist of three tyres, the two tyres are fitted in back legs and one freely movable is in the front of the cart, due to which the cart can rotates in left right direction. We simply cut the back two legs with tyres and weld two metal sheets. These metal sheets have three holes for screws that are used to fix he Power Window Motors to the metal sheet. The metal sheets are tough hard, which are able to lift 10kg to 15 kg weight, and main hole for the shaft of the motors. After the welding of two metal sheets our cart is all set to proceed the development, fitting motors, welding shafts to motors and the putting tyres to shafts. We used two metal sheets to provide strong support for the motors and specially for the shopping cart. These sheets are welded with back legs of the shopping cart with same positions, because we are provided that the cart motion will be straight as possible. The motors are fixed in the metal sheets through small bolts, each motors is fixed through three bolts, the cart also has a front tyre, which can move freely in any direction. The front tyre consist of a small bearing through which the cart can moves freely. The two tyres in back portion are mechanically lock means they cannot move when the shaft of the motors has not started to rotates. When the shafts start rotation the tyres will start movement.

4.2.2 Sitting Motors

After welding the metal sheets to the back legs of the cart, we weld shafts to the motors. Then we place motors into the metal sheet fixed with screws and put tyres into the shafts. Then we tied nuts on each bolt to fix the tyres hardly.

Figure 4.2 : Cart tyres setup

4.2.3 Welding A Free Tyre In Front Of Cart

As we fixed two tyres in back legs of the cart. We weld a freely movable tyre in front that is useful for the change in direction of the cart.

Figure 4.3: Front Tyre

4.2.4 Four Channels Relay Circuit description:

An Four Channels Relay is a type of circuit that can use to get a reversible DC motor to spin both clockwise and counterclockwise. In other words, this circuit allows to quickly reverse the direction a motor is spinning by using a switch or controller chip to change its direction

In a Relay there is a series of four controllable switches in which there are two sets of two switches. One set of switches when closed allows electricity to flow in one way. The other set of switches allow electricity to flow in the opposite direction. Another important characteristic of an Relay is that it typically can use a smaller voltage (5VDC from a micro controller, for instance) to control a much larger voltage (12VDC used to power a motor).

These two separate voltage sources are kept isolated from one another. Four Channels Relay can be made with either 4 relays or 4 transistors. The best type of Relay is made with transistors since these can easily be used to control a motor's speed (by using the smaller voltage to modulate the much larger motor voltage). An H-bridge made using relays (like the one are making) cannot easily be used to change a motor's speed (unless, of course, the motor voltage is being supplied from a power source capable of being modulated i.e. the H-bridge itself cannot modulate the power source to down the motor. The power must be decreased to slow down the motor before it goes through the H-bridge). This means that the motor will spin as fast as it can be in one direction and then when reversed spin as fast as it can in the other direction. The only thing that will slow down the spin of the motor is a controller that can modulate the 9VDC the power signal before it enters the H-bridge.

Figure 4.4:H- Bridge Relay Circuit Principle

When the coils on “Relay A1” and “Relay B2” are pulled high (electricity is flowing through them) then the motor will spin forwards. When the coils on “Relay B1” and “Relay A2” are pulled high (electricity is flowing through them) then the motor will spin backwards. When

the coils on “Relay A1” and “Relay B1” are pulled high (electricity is flowing through them) then the motor will stop spinning. When the coils on “Relay A2” and “Relay B2” are pulled high (electricity is flowing through them), then the motor will stop spinning. In the project this circuit is used as H –bridge relay circuit for controlling actuators to move forward and backward as shown figure 4.7:

Figure 4.5: Relay

4.2.5 Working Principle of Ultrasonic Sensors

The Ultrasonic sensors are used in our project to measure distance and to detect obstacles. The ultrasonic sensor is a four pin sensor in which one pin is VCC, GND, ECHO, and a TRIGGER pin. The VCC and GND are connected to 5 volt dc source while the echo and trigger is connected to the arduino uno. The ultrasonic sensor produce a sound wave in a specific frequency and transmitted, if the wave or signal is bounced by some obstacle then the sensor catch the bounced back signal and decided with the help of arduino to move more or stop.

Figure 4.6: Working of Ultrasonic Sensor

4.2.6 Working Principle of IR Sensors

The IR sensors are installed in the project that makes the cart to follow the customer. The IR sensors have both the Receiver and Transmitter. The motion of the cart is done due to the operation of both sensors. The receiver module has a range of 18 meters, while the transmitter has 20 cm. The receiver has a photodiode which act as a receiver head of infrared radiations.

Figure 4.7: Working of IR Sensors

4.2.7 Sensors Interface with Arduino

The sensors are interfaced with the arduino uno to for detection purpose. The sensors are connected to arduino by means of pins. Each sensors has a data or signal pin, a triggering pin, 5 Volts Vcc, and a GND pin. We common all the Vcc and GND pins of the sensors and connect them to the output of Buck converter. After this the data pins are connected to the Digital pins of audino as shown in Figure.

Figure 4.8: Sensors Interfaced

4.3 Description of Circuit

The project is divided into two parts, Receiver part, and Transmitter part. The receiver part mainly consists of arduino uno, motor driver circuit, ultrasonic and IR sensors and dc motors. The motors are driven by the four channel relay that is directed by arduino uno and arduino nano on the basis of sensors. The transmitter part is consist of belt in which sensors and an arduino nano is installed. The description is given below.

4.3.1 Receiver Circuit

The Receiver circuit is installed in the front of cart and is implemented on a glass sheet. It consists of Power window motors, arduino, motor driver, different sensors, and buck converter module. The cart goes forward, backward, left and right as the ir receiver sensors detect the transmitter rays. Three ultrasonic sensors are used to detect obstacle and make the stop commands, in which two are installed in left and right sides of the cart, while one is in the front of the cart. Three IR receiver modules are used in front and left right for the implementation of following the cart behind the customer. An adjustable buck converter is used to provide 5 volts supply to whole circuit.

Figure 4.9: Receiver Circuit

4.3.1 Transmitter Circuit

The transmitter circuit is consist of Arduino Nano, IR Transmitter LEDs, 5 Volts Cell. These components are assembled in a box, that box will be wear by customers and the cart will follow him. The IR LEDs transmits infra red rays and these rays are received by IR receiver module, due to this the arduino sends commands to motor driver to drive the cart forward, backward or left right or stop. The cart will stop at specified distance from the customer as the ultrasonic sensors in the cart detect the customer in range of 0.2 or 0.1 meters.

Figure 4.10: Transmitter

4.4 Project Implementation

4.4.1 Introduction

This chapter contains the hardware installation of the project. The first step in this phase is the selection of appropriate tool. The decision of tool selection is very crucial and important, so it should be wise enough to avoid any ambiguity and difficulty. For project implementation the thing is note able to select the software and hardware that are suitable to design and simulate the project in a software.

The project consists of two elements:

- Software
- Hardware

4.4.2 Software

There are multiple aspects to the software design of this project.

- Fritzing.
- Arduino Software for Arduino programming.

4.4.3 Software Simulation

For any project to work in a close environment, first we have to implement it on the software for the results and how our project will work. The software simulation is the testing of a project in a compatible software, all the parameters required by the components are put in there libraries. Once all the input parameters are completed, then we start simulation. The project design or model will implement in real also then it should be projected in a software also for the simulation testing. We make our project in proteus software that is used for electronic circuits. The software used is "Proteus" for the simulation's Here our project simulation below.

Figure 4.11: Software simulation

4.4.4 Arduino Software

The coding of moving forward, backward, left, right and stopping the cart been done in the environment of Arduino. The Arduino software is used to write little programs which the microcontroller should perform. These programs are called Sketch, In the end the sketches are transferred to the microcontroller by USB cable. A program for Arduino may be written in any programming language for a compiler that produces binary machine code for the target processor. Atmel provides a development environment for their microcontrollers, AVR Studio and the newer Atmel Studio.

The Arduino project provides the Arduino integrated development environment (IDE) which is a cross-platform application written in the programming language Java. It originated from the IDE for the languages Processing and Wiring. It includes a code editor with features such as text cutting and pasting, searching and replacing text, automatic indenting, brace matching, syntax highlighting and provides simple one-click mechanisms to compile and upload programs to an Arduino board. It also contains a message area, a text console, a toolbar with buttons for common functions and a hierarchy of operation menus. The Arduino IDE supports the languages C and C++ using special rules of code structuring [35].

Figure 4.12: Arduino 1.6.6 Software

4.4.5 Final Hardware

Various hardware tools were required to turn the design into reality. The main components of our project are Four Channels Relay, Arduino Uno, Arduino Nano, Power Window Motors, Infra Red Receiver and transmitter modules. The Four Channels Relay working on the principal of NO, NC Switches. The operation of Normally open and normally closed is done by electro magnetic field of the coil in the relay. The arduino is used to control the whole circuit by logic commands specified in the programming. The implemented and complete Hardware of the project is shown in the figure

Figure 4.13: Complete Hardware

Final Hardware:

CHAPTER NO 5

RESULTS, CONCLUSION AND FUTURE RECOMMENDATION

5.1 Results

The purpose of this project we developed is to make the shopping easier for the customers. As a result the automatic human following cart has been made. And we bring a successful and user friendly cart in the market. The intention of the project was to reduce the effort & to make easy shopping for humans. With our project, customers can enjoy shopping without pushing shopping cart themselves. The cart will follow a customer when he wears the belt and press the power buttons in the belt as well as in cart. The cart will follow the customer and will stop at a specific distance of 0.2 meter.

5.2 Conclusion

After along progress and hard work we developed the project "Automatic Human Following Shopping Cart" the facilitation for people at different places such as industrial, Superstores, Mega Malls, Airports. We convert a simple shopping cart to an automatic following cart. The motors are driven and control by Four Channel relay, and the whole system is managing and commanding by Arduino. Different sensors are interfaced with the Arduino uno for following, and stop purpose.

5.3 Future Recommendation

5.3.1 Automatic Billing System

The Automatic Billing System is to add the price of all the items put into the cart by the customer. All the things in mega malls, Superstores have a price labelled on it, the automatic billing system is more useful and time saving system for the customers, because if some collected thing in a Superstore the he will go the counter manager of the Superstore, and will stand in line waiting for the total bill of the items, so this is a difficult and time wasting. Due to instalment of the Automatic Billing System the customer will not stand and wait in line,

but the system will add and generate the total bill, and will gave the customer a short slip of item names, numbers, and total count. The generated slip will be shown to the Counter manager by the customer and directly will get free.

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APPENDIX

Arduino Code Programming:

Transmitter Code:

```
#include <IRremote.h>

IRsend irsend;

void setup()

{

}

void loop()

{

  for (int i = 0; i < 10; i++)

  {

    irsend.sendSony(0xa90, 12);

    delay(40);

  }

  delay(100);

}
```

Left Right Arduino Code:

```
#include <IRremote.h>

int RECV_PIN = 3;

const int D_OUT = 6;

IRrecv irrecv(RECV_PIN);

decode_results results;

void setup()

{
```

```

Serial.begin(9600);

irrecv.enableIRIn(); // Start the receiver

pinMode(D_OUT, OUTPUT);

digitalWrite(D_OUT, HIGH);

}

void loop()

{

if (irrecv.decode(&results))

{

Serial.println(results.value);

if(results.value== 2704)

{

digitalWrite(D_OUT, LOW);

delay(1000);

digitalWrite(D_OUT, HIGH);

}

irrecv.resume(); // Receive the next value

}

}

```

Receiver Code:

```
#include <IRremote.h>
```

```
#include <HCSR04.h>
```

```
UltrasonicDistanceSensor distanceSensor(7,8);
```

```
int RECV_PIN = 11;
```

```
const int L_SENSOR = 3;
const int R_SENSOR = 12;

int DIST;

IRrecv irrecv(RECV_PIN);

decode_results results;

void setup()
{
  Serial.begin(9600);
  irrecv.enableIRIn(); // Start the receiver

  Serial.println(" Waiting for signals");

  pinMode(A0, OUTPUT); // IN1
  pinMode(A1, OUTPUT); // IN2
  pinMode(A2, OUTPUT); // IN3
  pinMode(A3, OUTPUT); // IN4

  pinMode(L_SENSOR, INPUT);
  pinMode(R_SENSOR, INPUT);

  digitalWrite(A0, HIGH);
```

```

digitalWrite(A1, HIGH);
digitalWrite(A2, HIGH);
digitalWrite(A3, HIGH);

digitalWrite(L_SENSOR, HIGH);
digitalWrite(R_SENSOR, HIGH);
}
void loop()
{
    DIST = distanceSensor.measureDistanceCm();
    Serial.println(DIST);

    if(DIST>20)
    {
        if (irrecv.decode(&results))
        {
            if(results.value== 2704)
            {

                while(DIST>20) // if distance greater than 20 cm
                {
                    FWD();
                    DIST = distanceSensor.measureDistanceCm();
                }
            }
        }
        STOP();
    }
}

```

```
digitalWrite(A0, LOW);  
digitalWrite(A1, HIGH);  
digitalWrite(A2, LOW);  
digitalWrite(A3, HIGH);  
Serial.println(" FWD");  
}
```

```
void REV()  
{  
  digitalWrite(A0, HIGH);  
  digitalWrite(A1, LOW);  
  digitalWrite(A2, HIGH);  
  digitalWrite(A3, LOW);  
}
```

```
void RIGHT()  
{  
  digitalWrite(A0, LOW);  
  digitalWrite(A1, HIGH);  
  digitalWrite(A2, HIGH);  
  digitalWrite(A3, LOW);  
}
```

```
void LEFT()  
{
```

```
digitalWrite(A0, HIGH);  
digitalWrite(A1, LOW);  
digitalWrite(A2, LOW);  
digitalWrite(A3, HIGH);  
  
}
```

```
void STOP()  
{  
  digitalWrite(A0, HIGH);  
  digitalWrite(A1, HIGH);  
  digitalWrite(A2, HIGH);  
  digitalWrite(A3, HIGH);  
  Serial.println(" STOP");  
}
```